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THE IMPLICATIONS OF HUMAN RELATIONSHIP APPROACH TO EDUCATIONAL ADMINISTRATION

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Abstract

In educational scenario pupils are clients or outputs of school and colleges. They are not processed or programmed or manipulated. The learning program or process is purely built on personal relationships between, Managers, teachers, pupils, parents, community members, organizers and administrators. Even leaders, politicians, officers, inspectors and local bodies have their access to the educational administration. All human being responsible at their own positions and places have cordial relationships with each other. It gives an effective and efficient impetus to the educational process. This paper attempts to examine and explain the human relations theory, theoretical perspective of various scholars, the essence and impact of this theory on educational administration, also effort would be made to examine some critical views beside the theory.

Key Words: Human Relations, Education, School, Administration, Management

Introduction

The objective of educational institutions is much more difficult to define than the purpose of commercial organization. There are clear-cut educational equivalents to such major private sector objectives as profit maximization of product diversification. Schools and colleges are to develop personal abilities of the individuals, to inculcate the accepted values and beliefs to prepare pupils for the next stage of education or for employment. In this industry give and take or teach and learn is the main maxim of administration, where at both ends human beings are

involved giver as well as taker i.e. human beings. This way approach to the management of educational institutions markedly depends upon human relationship.

Mary Parker Follett (1933) who was convinced that no one could become a whole person except a member of the group. Thus ‘Learner’ and ‘Educator’ though share a common platform and have common purpose, but all this process is interactive and integrative effort of every individual from every group to frame a ‘holistic’ model. Cohesiveness of the group is important to make an activity productive. Cohesiveness is the product of inter personal relationship between all involved in the teaching learning activity. A frame work for the study of educational administration, formulated in terms of actual interacting persons, was developed by Jacob W. Getzels, Guba and Thalen based on three major dimensions: (1) Individual with personality and needs; (2) Group with its climate and intentions, and (3) Institutions with roles and expectations.

In the human relationship approach in educational administration, the importance of individuals working in the organization, and in particular, their views, needs and prejudices dominate. The need of teachers and schools are complementary, each requires the other. If they don’t match, both suffer. The teacher will not be able to achieve, school will fail to meet its objective. If they fit each other, objectives are achieved as suited to the salient features. So relationship approach helps education to achieve effective results. The business in educational administration is oriented with teaching, nurturing, simulating and providing a healthy and supportive learning climate for children. The effective use of motivational theories and methods play a significant role in student teacher, teacher principal, principal community, and principal administration relation. The motivational theories also probe into relationship among ends, as behaviour, rewards, satisfaction and productivity.

For many years there has been a demand for a new content in the teaching of school administration. The vast amount of interest and research has demonstrated clearly that the new content is people. It is concerned with the behaviour of people in the social institution known as the school. The frame of reference of educational administration is the administrator, but it carries importance to teachers, students, parents, and that indefinable person, the lay citizen. If one is to know about behaviour, one cannot stay within the confines of any single discipline and

expect to gain real insights. This discussion about school administration draws upon psychology, with its many branches and subdivisions, sociology, perception, group dynamics, political science, anthropology, business and industrial administration, and educational administration. All of these have much to offer. Educational administration is not a pure science in itself, and so it must draw upon all areas of investigation. The relevant findings must be synthesized and focused upon the problems and issues of school administration in such a way that a theory will someday be constructed.

The basic assumption is that human behaviour can be changed. Through the use of substantive knowledge, actual situations or cases, meaningful exercises, and the case method of discussion in the classroom, the administrator can gain new insights into the people with whom he works. He will have no need for a list of techniques; in fact, he will grow to be quite suspicious of this approach to human relations.

Human relations approach to educational administration

The implications of a human relations approach to educational administration are numerous. First off, a human relations approach steers managerial focus towards an emphasis on employee enthusiasm, morale and contentment rather than just productivity alone. An emphasis on this democratic approach developed the term democratic administration. This in turn influenced a more democratic approach to administration in teaching, leadership strategies, decisions, etc. The emphasis on human relations and democratic style in turn developed what is termed principles of administration. This entails suppositions of how things should be or how individuals should behave within the realm of an organization.

A school in which a principal utilizes a human relations perspective is one in which the staff feel they are able to work freely as a team without coercion or manipulation from administration. Suffice to say, most educators prefer a work environment as such. This environment is one in which administrators do not hover over teachers and staff, suspiciously monitor work, or deliver commands in a hostile or threatening manner.

Instead, the school with a human relations perspective embodies an atmosphere in which relational aspects such as developing and maintaining positive relationships are deemed of high importance. In addition, the campus environment is one of high teacher morale. Staff members are enthusiastic about coming to work every day and genuinely excited to be a part of the school team. In this campus, the Principal sets a tone of encouragement and embraces the concept of employees as important individuals who are capable of influencing the school in a positive manner through their own unique skills. It is a pleasant environment.

The overall result of this approach is an environment consisting of collaborative and harmonious relationships amongst staff members ranging from paraprofessionals to administration. Most importantly, the faculty's behaviour is highly motivated and passionate regarding the vision of the school. The principal who leads a school with a human relations approach places an emphasis on employee satisfaction and motivation.

In this manner, the success of a school is contingent upon the high satisfaction of the staff. If staff members are happy, motivated and satisfied with the school environment, they in turn are highly productive and achieve successful results as a team. An emphasis on a human relations approach generally leads to a more enjoyable and productive work atmosphere. If only administrators would not lose sight of this basic, but fundamental approach to leadership in the pursuit of demanding expectations of success. After all, even educators deserve to work in a healthy and pleasant environment.

Human relations in personnel administration

Human relations in administration simply means accomplishing the goals of the organization without friction. It presupposes a knowledge of the goals and the needs of individuals belonging to the group. In an educational set-up the official responsible for accomplishing the goals of the school revolves on the teacher and the personnel officer, if any. Usually in the India setting the teacher is the personnel officer at the same time.

It is easier to administer a small school than a big one because there are fewer people to know and deal with and there is more chance of knowing the people better in a small group. However, in bigger libraries there are division chiefs and section heads who will help the principal in administration. On the choice, therefore, of these heads rests the success of the function of coordination and cooperation.

An administrator who can be democratic and fair, and who can meet the emotional needs of his staff will surely be a success. If s/he is democratic s/he will make rules in cooperation with the staff and will treat them as equals (1). S/he will not be judgemental (2) in his/her relations but rather helpful by seeing the other fellow's point of view. S/he will open all channels of communication freely. S/he will try to meet the emotional needs of his men by accepting each one as s/he really is; knowing his/her problems and ambitions s/he can coordinate them with the goals of the school; s/he provides affection by showing interest in everyone's welfare; and lastly s/he provides room for achievement. He sets a good example for them to follow.

It is more or less know the principles and the do's and don'ts of administration. Our difficulty lies in the interpretation of these principles in actual practice. We are all human and we all commit mistakes. Sometimes we are not aware of our mistakes because we have to attend to so many things and we are but human in thinking that we try to do the right things. Therefore, we will confine our self to cases so that when we get into a parallel situation we will know whether we fared badly or well. All these cases are made up only.

As the leader of the organization the principal sets the tone of the administration, whether it is democratic or authoritarian. He may formulate democratic rules but in practice he might deviate from them without his being aware of it. The littlest act, a word uttered at the wrong moment may give him away. The staff can feel his/her sincerity and fairness in many little ways. No matter how the best policies are written if the administrator deviates in his/her actions, the staff will always take note. They are most sensitive to faults.

Human relations theory and school administration

The human relations movement started between 1935-1950. It was a radical reaction to the scientific movement which treated human being as machines. The principles of human relations believed that organizations should see and treat the workers as human beings. It was a product of what is known as the Hawthorne studies, by George Elton Mayo, which examined the effects of social relation, motivation and employee satisfaction on productivity. Elton stressed the following: "Natural groups, in which social aspects take precedence over functional organizational structure Upwards communication, is two way, from worker to chief executive, as well as vice versa. Cohesion and good leadership is needed to communicate goals and to ensure effective and coherent decision making".

Mary Parket Follet (1868-1933) believed that the fundamental problem in all organization was in developing and maintaining dynamic and harmonious relationships. According to Mary Follet, a prominent pioneer of the new line in National Society for the Study of Education (1964); "it is not just a production and distribution of manufactured articles, it is also to give opportunity for individual development and self-actualization through better organization of human relationships. The process of production is as important as that of the welfare of the society as product of production".

The formal work group the social environment employees has great influence on the productivity. To Mayo and others, the concept of social man (motivated by social needs, wanting-on the-job relationships and more responsive to work group pressure than to management control) has to replace the old concept of rational man motivated by personal economic needs. This theory marked the beginning of the recognition of human factor in the effectiveness of an organization. Other proponents of the Human Relations Theory are Douglas McGregor, Chris Agris and Abraham Maslow. Under the human relations movement we can put McGregor's theory X and Y and Maslow's theory of hierarchy of needs.

Theory X and Y

Oreamesi (2001) advanced that Doulas McGregor's in his book "The human side of enterprise" postulated dichotomous view of the attitudes of managers towards employees. The two

theoretical assumptions which are separately known as theory X and Y present diverse perception of the relationships between manager and subordinates in organizational life. Theory X portends a pessimistic view of workers. It assumes that employees are inherently lazy and will avoid work if they can. As a result of this management believes that workers need to be closely supervised and comprehensive systems of control developed. According to Michael (2011) if organizational goals are to be met, theory X managers rely heavily on threat and coercion to gain the employees compliance.

Theory Y presents a different orientation about the relationships between managers and employees. In this theory management assumes employees may be ambitious and self-motivated and exercise self control. It also believes that employees enjoy their mental and physical work. Its goes further to state that to them work is as natural as play and the average human being does not inherently dislike work, given the proper conditions, theory Y managers believe that employees will learn to seek out and accept responsibility and to exercise self-control and self-direction in accomplishing objectives to which they are committed.

Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs

According to Abraham Maslow, man always has needs to satisfy. These needs can be satisfied in a hierarchical order starting from the basic needs to the higher order needs. The theory further explains that once a particular need is satisfied, it ceases to be a motivator and another one arises. He classified needs into:

- *Physiological*: Basic physical needs like air, food, shelter, water.
- *Safety*: The need for physical and psychological security.
- *Social*: The desire for satisfying social relationships with others, like acceptance and feeling of belonging.
- *Ego*: This is the need for self-respect, recognition and appreciation by management.
- *Self actualization*: The desire to be an that one can be

Maslow succeeded in classifying human needs as least as an aid thinking for management. What is disputed in Maslow's theory is the issue of successive saturation. Satisfying one need can help alleviate another, therefore they overlap.

The essence and impact of the Human Relations theory on Educational Administration

The human relations theory occupied a great role in the development of organizational administration. During the era of Human Relations theory, numerous themes, ideas or notions were emphasized in education administration. The human relations school of management thought, which emphasized treating employees in a human manner, has impact in the educational administration in several ways (Kimbough & Nunnery 1983). These include:

- Increasing effort to democratize the practice of educational administration.
- Growing emphasis on the utilization of concept from the social sciences, anthropology, psychology, sociology and the behavioural elements of economics and political sciences.
- Educational administrators were responsible for the promotion of relations between organization members that were mutually satisfying. Harmony and high staff morale were considered essentials for improved teaching and learning.
- This movement also proposed the implementation of methods of dealing with workers as a psychological being. E.g. Teachers and non-academic staff in school system etc.
- Educational administrators began to stress the exercise of group authority within the legal frame work governing educational organizations.
- Human relations is seen as an attempt of humanization of labour that is of practical value for increasing profits and social responsibility.
- There emerged an increasing emphasis and support among educational administrators participative or cooperative decision making.
- It aims at addressing the social needs of workers and therefore elicits their cooperation as a workforce.
- Finally, the advocates of democratic administration stressed that the executive educational administrator should take steps to satisfy psychological needs.

It made educational administration come to be seen as service activities contributing to the effective instructional programmes, as a means and not an end itself. Mochlman (1940), put this idea more clearly and when he stated that: “Administration in essentially a services activity, a tool or agency through the fundamental objectives of the educational process may be more fully and efficiently realized”.

Criticisms of Human Relations theory

The human relations movement made very significant contribution to management thought. It brought into limelight human and social factors in organizations; it made management to regard workers as human beings rather the cogs in the machinery. Furthermore, human relations movement led to the emergence of participative management or decision making. It stressed the significance social or informal group in the organization. It also brought about the humanizing of management and sense of flexibility in bureaucratic enterprise. Finally, it led to a lessening of the emphasis on “one best way” of getting a work done.

In spite of its contributions, human relations approached ideas and practices have a number of criticism. In many case. Human relations programmes were implemented as a technique for manipulating people to comply with management directives instead of for bringing management to an understanding of human nature and thereby creating the desirable changes in the organization. Human Relations is also criticized for overemphasizing human needs at the expense of need for accomplishment or responsibility, or for organizational task and process. Subsequently, there was lack of comprehensiveness in the notion advanced.

The effect of human relations theories did not result in the demise of the numerous applications of classical theory. Some of the postulates advanced by human relations theorists did not give the rise of derivations that were subject to empirical testing. There was a lack of evidence of confirm some of the derivations from the postulates advanced. For instance, Unde (2007) pointed out that the evidence is less conclusive with regard to the often assumed relationship between increase employee satisfaction and increased productivity. Human resources-oriented theories of the latter

of the era generally assumed that good and meaningful performance leads to job satisfaction and not the reverse.

Human relations theories' idea posed certain dilemmas without solutions offered. For example, several of the theorists stressed the importance of satisfying both individual needs and organizational goals, but in the event of unresolved conflict between the two, what should be the direction. This work is considered by academics as counterpart to Taylorism and scientific management.

CONCLUSION

Human relations movement emerged around 1930s in USA to cope with dehumanization of individuals in organizations; it emphasized on the study of the behaviour of workers in organizations, and examined the effects of social relations, motivation and employee satisfaction on productivity. The theory makes school administrators to view workers in terms of their psychology and fit within the school system rather than as inter-challengeable parts. The importance of human beings engaged by an enterprise for the realization of its goals and the realization of the importance is the easier aspect of the problems. The more difficult part being the actual creation and continuous maintenance of the willingness and happiness. Knowledge of the behaviour of a man, as an Individual and as a member of various groups for Instance, human elements in primary or any level of education is scanty, disorganized and is in the early process of evolution. Effectiveness of an administration aims at the achievement of organisation goals. As such school administration could therefore be said to be the extent to which the goals of the school system are accomplished by the head teachers, teachers, pupils and others within the school community. Thus, the framework within which the people and environment interact should be considered.

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